

Introduction to Engineering Design

Chapter 5

Design Conceptualisation

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Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. To develop a conceptual design
2. To identify broad design parameters in innovation

3.0 Introduction

This week's (fifth) topics correspond to the fourth-course objectives, which state, "Develop a conceptual design with the material specification based on broad design parameters including cost and sustainability".

The fourth week's topics respond to the first-course objective, "To identify and apply the various phases and processes within an engineering design process".

The third week's topics discuss communication, collaboration and team success, even in a diverse team membership or multi-disciplinary nature.

The second week's response to the second-course objective states, "On completion of this subject, the students can participate within and contribute to a multi-discipline engineering design team through the application of team roles and communication". It also

In the first week's discussion, the challenge to take part in the Sustainable Development Goals action using the Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) that served as a theme to the Engineering Design Challenge 2022, was taken on board as an engineering design team is discussed and organised in the second week.

3.1 Design Conceptualisation

3.1.1 Definition of Conceptual Design:

- 1) The ability to invent or formulate an idea or concept.

2) Design conceptualisation is generating ideas for an optimum solution to the design problem. These ideas should stem originally from the product idea and stated definitions of the design problem (Mogahzy)

3) Conceptual design is a framework for establishing the underlying idea behind a design and a plan for how it will be expressed visually. (Levanier)

- The conceptualisation starts in the initial design stage of the project. Where the project's scope is drafted, and a list of the desired design features and requirements is created. (Conceptualization)
- Conceptual design has the root word “concept,” which describes the idea and intention behind the design. (Levanier)
- The purpose of conceptual design is to give a shape via visual to an idea. (Levanier)
- Three main facets to the goals of conceptual design: (Levanier)
 - ✓ To establish a basis of logic
 - ✓ To create a design language
 - ✓ To achieve originality
- The conceptual design approach can be broken down into four steps.
 - ✓ **1. Definition.** You must start your design project by asking why the project is necessary. What is the specific goal of the design, and what problem is it meant to solve?
 - ✓ **2. Research.** Design concepts must be grounded in research. It starts with getting information on the client —their brand, history, mission, and personality. And the market, conduct target audience research to understand what's in a design they are looking for.

Searching for similar designs from competitors can help you understand industry conventions and give you ideas for setting your concept apart. Research the work of other designers to gather reference material and inspiration, especially from those you find particularly masterful. Doing so can show you conceptual possibilities you might never have imagined, challenging you to push your concepts. (Levanier)

Design research not only aims at the formulation and validation of models and theories about the phenomenon of design but also the development and validation of knowledge, methods and tools founded on these theories to improve the design process. One of the challenges is that the topic of study, design, is a purposeful, complex and powerfully dynamic activity involving artefacts, people, tools, processes, and organisations, as well as the micro- and macro-environment in which it takes place.

Figure 20 illustrates the aims of engineering design research. It highlights the various aspects involved in the design that should be studied or taken into account

in design research. A combination of factors usually reviews typical engineering design research.

Figure 20. Design research aims and aspects involved in the design

- ✓ **3. Verbal ideation.** To shape a concept into something solid, speaking it out is to draw some of those words out. This phase is known as brainstorming, where you define your concept verbally.
 - ✓ **4. Visual ideation.** Concepts must leap from abstract ideas to a visual design through sketching.
- ✓ A product team (design team) creates a working design concept for a new product through three steps: (Design Concept)
- ✓ 1: Find a problem worth solving.
It is knowing your user persona's goals and challenges and also, researching the market. A problem worth solving for the user will be one that your target customer may be willing to pay.
 - ✓ 2: Set your design parameters.

Take your product idea and give it some form and context, such as size, shape, and materials for a physical product; the look and feel of the product is digital.

- ✓ 3: A short design concept statement draft.

A statement to tell stakeholders about the plan and expectations for the new product should be short, clear, and easy to understand.

- ✓ A design concept needs to accomplish the following. (Design Concept)

- ✓ 1. Communicate the problem the product solves.

What will the product do?

A product design concept should explain both what the product will do for users (the solution) and why that functionality will add value to their lives (the problem they're looking to overcome).

- ✓ 2. Identify the product's target user.

Who is the product for?

A design concept should describe on a personal level the people your product will help—and how the user experience will be tailored to serve those people.

- ✓ 3. Describe how the user will interact with the product.

The goal is to convey to stakeholders what you plan, hope, and expect for your new product idea. The statement should be short, clear, and easy to understand. It should also communicate all three of the details we discussed above: the problem your product will solve, its intended user, and an overview of the user's experience.

3.2 Innovation

Definition: Innovation is insight that leads a scientist, engineer or inventor to investigate an issue or phenomenon by observing things around him. (What Do We Mean by "Innovation"?)

- ✓ Innovation-driving criteria in continuous improvement and commitment to excellence.
- ✓ Innovation is sparked by curiosity, taking risks, by experimenting or testing its assumptions. The innovation is based on questioning and challenging the status quo. It is also based on recognising opportunity and taking advantage of it. (What Do We Mean by "Innovation"?)

Five critical dimensions that innovators can use to think through and conceptualise the idea. (Balasubramanian)

1. **Competitive advantage:** This is the unique selling proposition for the idea. It is the key differentiating factor for a unique competitive position of the enterprise in the marketplace brought about by the idea generated.

Example1: Nintendo was successful with the Wii gaming console due to its unique qualities compared to Sony's PlayStation and Microsoft's Xbox, their competitor. Nintendo focused on customers' desire to play, which gives them an advantage over their competitors by focusing on the graphics engine component of the console.

Example 2: iPod's differentiating factor that makes them unique is the positioning in combination with iTunes. It allows iTunes customers to buy tracks of customers interest rather than the entire album that others are selling strategy. Apple also made a simple and attractive interface to further differentiate from its competitors.

2. **Business alignment:** The innovator needs to relate the idea to the enterprise's current and future business directions. The conceptualised idea is around the key strategic focus of the business and its goals. Considering how the idea leverages the enterprise's core competencies is also essential.

Example: 3Ms like Post-it notes innovations, including photographic films and magnetic tape, are the results of leveraging expertise in substrates, coatings and adhesives. RIM's success with the Blackberry smartphone creates an advantage based on design features the company's strategic focus on enterprise business. The Blackberry PlayBook, RIM's recent innovation, is based on its enterprise-centric features.

3. **Customers:** Is knowing the customers idea is very important in conceptualisation.

Example: Blackberry clearly views its customer as partner in their business. The result features in its PlayBook tablet device. Nintendo defined a broader customer centered through gaming focusing on attracting females and families in addition to hardcore gamers, gains success against dominated market by Sony and Microsoft and bet them in their strategy. Key learning in this example for an innovator is to define the customer needs and, understand their wants and conceptualise the unique differentiators and what is perceived as necessary for the particular market segment.

4. **Execution:** Execution is the complementing capabilities that develop the idea into a successful innovation and take it to business. The innovator works in incubating the idea, available technologies best suited to develop the idea, and how to co-create by leveraging the business competencies. Other factors in success are identification of resources, processes, risks, partners and suppliers and the ecosystem.

Example: Apple had to build an ecosystem of its engineers, the designers, the manufacturing plants, the suppliers for components, and the agreements with music labels to launch the iPod and iTunes successfully. They continuously expanded their ecosystem to develop the App Stores, which have contributed significantly to the success of the iPad. Some execution tasks are required in the later stages of the innovation life cycle,

particularly in business incubation and commercialisation. It is, nevertheless, essential for the innovator to articulate an execution plan.

5. **Business value:** It refers to the mechanism that brings value to the business in pursuing the idea. It covers how revenues will be generated, the market size, how it is shared with the partners, the cost structure and how profits are generated. This dimension addresses the crucial benefits for the business in pursuing the idea and how the benefits are realised. The value definition is a critical aspect of the business model of the concept and forms the basis for the

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